

IMPACT OF APRIL 23-24, 2023 GEOMAGNETIC STORM ON THE GNSS POSITIONING AT CACHOEIRA PAULISTA

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The thermosphere-ionosphere-magnetosphere system is largely affected during events of geomagnetic storms. Its dynamics, mainly in the ionized environment, may impact modern lives by degradations in the satellite signals affecting, for example, all applications involving Global Navigation Satellite Systems. In this work, we present an analysis of how much the disturbed ionosphere can cause deviation in the position of a GNSS receiver as calculated by RTKLib [1]. The selected experimental data were registered during the large geomagnetic storm and at Cachoeira Paulista (CP, 22.7°S; 45°W and mag. Latitude = 21.75°S) between April 22-24, 2023 which the corresponding pairs of solar flux (F10.7) and geomagnetic activity (Ap) indexes (data available at https://chain-new.chain-project.net/echaim_downloads/apf107.dat) were (142.7; 06), (136.7; 65) and (135.5; 72), respectively. Detailed descriptions of this storm were recently published by [2] and [3]. Figure 1 shows the diurnal variations of the data for the sequence of three days, as described below. The first row is the effective wind, i.e., the wind speed along the magnetic field lines (blue dots) from the empirical model HWM14 [4] and also the respective velocity measurements of thermospheric neutral wind (red dots) by a Fabry-Pérot interferometer (FPI) and equatorial $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ vertical drift (black dots) by JULIA radar [5]. The ionospheric peak parameters hmF2 and foF2 are shown in the second and third rows, respectively. The vertical Total Electron Content (vTEC) is together with foF2. It is important to mention that vTECs were calibrated using the code from the University of Dallas at Texas (UTD). An IONEX file was produced for the Brazilian region (BR IONEX). In fact, the vTEC from the IGS IONEX were replaced by the values calculated by the UTD code. The wind velocity modeled and measurements of meridional (U_θ) and zonal (U_ϕ) components have been used to calculate effective winds. The northward effective wind (U_{eff}) was calculated by $U_{eff} = (U_\theta \cos D + U_\phi \sin D) \cos I$, where D and I are magnetic declination and dip angle, respectively. Since the day April 22 has a low Ap index (Ap = 6) it is considered representative of geomagnetic quiet conditions. All ionospheric parameters, as shown in Figure 1 first column, present no anomalous variations for this day. For example, the pre-reversal enhancement in the $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ vertical drift velocity occurs at the usual time (near midnight in universal time), as well as its consequence, the increased foF2/vTEC after midnight over CP. It is relevant to highlight two events registered during the disturbed days 23 and 24. A large eastward prompt penetration electric field (PPEF [6], see abrupt increase in $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ vertical drift (top middle panel)) occurred on first disturbed day (April 23) between 17:30-19:45 UT and a travelling atmospheric disturbance (TAD) on the second day around 4 UT (top right side panel). Unfortunately, no wind measurements were taken during the first two days analyzed. The ionospheric response to the PPEF is clearly seen simultaneously on foF2 and vTEC with an enhancement starting at 19:00 UT, as expected. Due to the well-known phenomenon called ionospheric fountain effect, the equatorial plasma is moved up to the highest altitude and, by diffusion process, reaches a low latitude like CP location. Also, the TAD produces significant variations in foF2 and vTEC near 4 UT. Maximum wind speeds toward the equator produced well-defined maxima (minima) in hmF2 (foF2 and TEC) at 4 UT on April 24. The foF2 and TEC minima are due to local plasma transport, driven by the motion of the meridional winds. The winds reverse direction after 4:30 UT, so the behavior of the mentioned ionospheric parameters also reverses. It is important to note that as soon as the conversion of the wind direction toward the poles occurs, the plasma moves downwards along the magnetic field lines, and before being destroyed by recombination, it accumulates ([3]; [7]). Therefore, maxima appear in foF2 and TEC, as shown in the third column and in the two last panels of Figure 1. The ionospheric effects

due to disturbed thermospheric wind over South America were discussed by [7] and [8]. A maxima in the ionospheric densities were explained by traveling waveform winds. The CP position was calculated using the RTKLib software, The dual-frequency Precise Point Positioning (PPP) with kinematic option and Single Frequency PPP (SF - PPP) with the IGS IONEX files and the BR IONEX produced in this work were used. To assess the impact of a disturbed ionosphere on the positioning, the absolute distances from the actual position of CP were calculated. Figure 2 presents the distances, for the mentioned options, obtained during the three days (22-24). Some discrepancies in the calculated positions for CP happen each day at ~1 UT. Such a time is coincident with a decreasing stage of the ionization crest. It is also important to mention that the largest position deviation occurred near the PPEF event around 20 UT and for all PPP options.

Figure 1 - Diurnal variations of effective wind, $E \times B$ vertical drift, hmF2, foF2 and vTEC over CP for April 22-24, 2023.

Fonte: Authors (2024).

One explanation for both cases may be attributed to the large local ionospheric gradients, which are not well represented in both IGS IONEX and the IONEX files produced in this work. Therefore, the main conclusion of this work is that the most significant impact on positioning errors in the CP sector occurred shortly after the eastward storm's electric field to

reach the highest level. Such an impact may be associated with the dynamics of the southern crest of the equatorial ionization anomaly.

Figure 2 – Diurnal variations of CP position deviation during April 22 to 24, 2023. Black dots are the deviation calculated using IGS IONEX maps and red one using BR IONEX obtained with UTD code. Bottom panels show PPP for dual-frequency.

Fonte: Authors (2024).

Keywords: Ionosphere; Geomagnetic storm; Thermospheric neutral wind; $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ vertical drift. Positioning by RTKLib.

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